

ISOLDE ion beam purification by ion bunch width manipulation via fast modulated heating of the RILIS laser ion source

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Project description:

The resonance ionization laser ion source (RILIS) is the principal ion source at ISOLDE, providing efficient and element-selective ion creation by laser radiation tuned to unique electronic transitions of the atoms of interest. The 10 kHz pulsed operation of the laser systems imprints a respective bunch structure on the extracted ion beam. This characteristic can be used to purify the ion beam from contamination by applying a synchronized beam gating, only letting the bunches of the laser-ionized species pass and suppress the contaminant DC-component in between. The efficacy of this method is enhanced if the ion bunch width can be reduced.

The bunch width is predominantly determined by the applied voltage gradient along the ion source that is required for an electric current of ~300 A to resistively heat the source to approximately 2000 °C. Decoupling of the voltage gradient from the operation temperature can be achieved by introducing a modulated, or pulsed, heating scheme: While the average dissipated power is kept constant to reach the defined temperature, the voltage is applied with a duty cycle. During on-time, the required electrical power (and ergo voltage) is accordingly higher. By synchronizing the laser system with this heating modulation in a 100 μs cycle time, ions of choice are created by the laser in the time frame of active heating and high voltage gradient, and therefore formed to a narrower ion bunch than they would be with a DC heating regime, as desired for more effective beam-gate selectivity.

Following previous exploration work [1], the project of development and testing of respective equipment for μs-switching of high currents in the range of up to 2000 A for the existing ISOLDE target/ion source system will be conducted in cooperation between the SY/STI and SY/ABT groups. While the former is responsible for ISOLDE target/ion source operation and development, the latter provides expertise in high current fast switching systems.

References:

[1] S. Rothe et al, Nucl Instrum Methods Phys Res B **376** (2016), 86–90; DOI: [10.1016/j.nimb.2016.02.060](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nimb.2016.02.060)